

Relevant ingredients of the massively parallel implementation of FETI methods

T. Kozubek^{a,*}, V. Vondrak^a, Z. Dostal^a, D. Horak^a, V. Hapla^a

^aDepartment of Applied Mathematics, VSB-TU of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 15, 70833 Ostrava, Czech Republic

Abstract

The bottlenecks related to the numerical solution of many engineering problems are very dependent on the techniques used to solve the systems of linear equations resulting from their linearizations and finite element discretizations. The large linearized problems can be solved efficiently using the so-called scalable algorithms based on multigrid or domain decomposition method. In cooperation with the Elmer team two variants of the domain decomposition method have been implemented into Elmer: (i) FETI-1 (Finite Element Tearing and Interconnecting) introduced by Farhat and Roux and (ii) Total FETI introduced by Dostal, Horak, and Kucera. In the latter the Dirichlet boundary conditions are torn off to have all subdomains floating which makes the method very flexible. In this paper, we review the relevant ingredients of the massively parallel implementation of FETI methods when they are applied on elliptic boundary value problems. More specifically, we describe effective assembling of the gluing matrix, regularization of the stiffness matrix, parallelization of the coarse problem solution, preconditioning etc. The performance is demonstrated on linear elasticity benchmarks solved by our Total FETI implementation using parallelization library PETSc on the HECToR machine at EPCC and using ELMER multiphysical simulation software on the French TIER-0 system CURIE.

1. Introduction

The goal of this paper is to describe an efficient massively parallel implementation of our variant of the FETI type domain decomposition method called Total FETI (TFETI) and demonstrate its efficiency using the PETSc and ELMER TFETI implementations on the TIER-1 and TIER-0 systems.

The key idea is to use the FETI method introduced by Farhat and Roux [1] for the numerical solution of the large linear systems arising in linearized engineering problems. Using this approach, a body is partitioned into non-overlapping subdomains, an elliptic problem with Neumann boundary conditions is defined for each subdomain, and intersubdomain field continuity is enforced via Lagrange multipliers. The Lagrange multipliers are evaluated by solving a relatively well conditioned dual problem of a small size that may be efficiently solved by a suitable variant of the conjugate gradient algorithm. The first practical implementations exploited only the favorable distribution of the spectrum of the matrix of the smaller problem [2], known also as the dual Schur complement matrix, but such algorithm was efficient only with a small number of subdomains. Later, Farhat, Mandel, and Roux introduced a “natural coarse problem” whose solution was implemented by auxiliary projectors so that the resulting algorithm became in a sense optimal [3, 4]. In our approach, we use the Total-FETI [5] variant of FETI domain decomposition method, where even the Dirichlet boundary conditions are enforced by Lagrange multipliers. Hence all subdomain stiffness matrices are singular with a-priori known kernels which is a great advantage in the numerical solution. With known kernel basis we can regularize effectively the stiffness matrix without extra fill in and use any standard Cholesky type decomposition method for nonsingular matrices [6].

Another relevant ingredient analyzed in the paper is the effective parallel implementation of the coarse problem solution which is defined by an orthogonal projection onto the kernel of the large and rectangular matrix appearing in the TFETI algorithm.

2. TFETI domain decomposition method

To apply the TFETI domain decomposition on a linear boundary value (e.g. Poisson or elasticity) problem defined in a domain Ω , we tear the body from the part of the boundary with the Dirichlet boundary condition,

*Corresponding author.

tel. +420 597 323 494 fax. +420 596 919 597 e-mail. tomas.kozubek@vsb.cz

We suppose that (4) is uniquely solvable which is guaranteed by the following necessary and sufficient conditions [8]:

$$Ker \mathbf{B}^\top = \{\mathbf{o}\}, \quad (5)$$

$$Ker \mathbf{K} \cap Ker \mathbf{B} = \{\mathbf{o}\}. \quad (6)$$

Notice that (5) is the condition on the full row-rank of \mathbf{B} . Let us mention that a basis of $Ker \mathbf{K}$ can be constructed directly using subdomain rigid body modes and assume that its vectors are columns of the matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times l}$, $l = n - rank(\mathbf{K})$. More precisely, in 2D each subdomain Ω^p is assigned three columns with the sections

$$\begin{bmatrix} -y_i & 1 & 0 \\ x_i & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

and the zero matrix $\mathbf{O} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 3}$ associated with each vertex $V_i \in \bar{\Omega}^p$ and $V_j \notin \bar{\Omega}^p$, respectively. Similarly in 3D each subdomain Ω^p is assigned six columns with the sections

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -z_i & y_i & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ z_i & 0 & -x_i & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -y_i & x_i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

and the zero matrix $\mathbf{O} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 6}$ associated with each vertex $V_i \in \bar{\Omega}^p$ and $V_j \notin \bar{\Omega}^p$, respectively.

The first equation in (4) is satisfied iff

$$\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{B}^\top \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \in Im \mathbf{K} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{K}^\dagger (\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{B}^\top \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}) + \mathbf{R} \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \quad (8)$$

for an appropriate $\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \in \mathbb{R}^l$ and arbitrary generalized inverse \mathbf{K}^\dagger satisfying $\mathbf{K} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}$. Moreover, (7) can be equivalently written as

$$\mathbf{R}^\top (\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{B}^\top \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}) = \mathbf{o}. \quad (9)$$

Further substituting (8) into the second equation in (4) we arrive at

$$-\mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{B}^\top \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{R} \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \mathbf{c} - \mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{f}. \quad (10)$$

Summarizing (9) and (10) we find that the pair $(\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}) \in \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^l$ satisfies:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F} & \mathbf{G}^\top \\ \mathbf{G} & \mathbf{O} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} \\ \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{d} \\ \mathbf{e} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{F} := \mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{B}^\top$, $\mathbf{G} := -\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{B}^\top$, $\mathbf{d} := \mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{c}$, and $\mathbf{e} := -\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{f}$. The system matrix of (11) is the (negative) *Schur complement* of \mathbf{K} in the system matrix of (4) and invertible [8], thus we can compute first $(\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})$ by solving (11) and then we obtain $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ from (8). Let us note that (11) has formally the same saddle-point structure as that of (4), however, its size is considerably smaller and the diagonal block $\mathbf{B} \mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{B}^\top$ is much better conditioned than \mathbf{K} .

Now we shall split (11) using the orthogonal projector $\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G}$ onto the so-called natural coarse space $Ker \mathbf{G}$. As (6) implies that \mathbf{G} is of full row-rank, we can identify $\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G}$ with the following matrix:

$$\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} := \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q}_\mathbf{G} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{Q}_\mathbf{G} := \mathbf{G}^\top (\mathbf{G} \mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1} \mathbf{G},$$

with $\mathbf{Q}_\mathbf{G}$ being the orthogonal projector onto the image space of \mathbf{G}^\top . Applying $\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G}$ on the first equation in (11) we obtain that $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ satisfies:

$$\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} \mathbf{F} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} \mathbf{d}, \quad \mathbf{G} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \mathbf{e}. \quad (12)$$

In order to arrange (12) as one equation on the vector space $Ker \mathbf{G}$ we decompose the solution $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ into $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Im} \in Im \mathbf{G}^\top$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker} \in Ker \mathbf{G}$ as

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Im} + \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker}. \quad (13)$$

Since $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Im}$ is easily available via

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Im} = \mathbf{G}^\top (\mathbf{G} \mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1} \mathbf{e},$$

it remains to show how to get $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker}$. Substituting (13) into (12) we can see that $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker}$ satisfies:

$$\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} \mathbf{F} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker} = \mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{F} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Im}), \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_{Ker} \in Ker \mathbf{G}. \quad (14)$$

Let us note that this equation is uniquely solvable, as $\mathbf{P}_\mathbf{G} \mathbf{F} : Ker \mathbf{G} \mapsto Ker \mathbf{G}$ is symmetric positive definite and invertible if the system matrix of (4) is invertible [8]. Finally note that, if $\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}$ is known, the solution component $\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$ is given by

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = (\mathbf{G} \mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1} \mathbf{G} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{F} \bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}). \quad (15)$$

Action of the matrix \mathbf{F} on a vector is perfectly parallelizable because of the block diagonal structure of \mathbf{K}^\dagger and the block structure of \mathbf{B} respecting the decomposition into subdomains. On the other hand, action of the projector \mathbf{P}_G is not directly parallelizable. Therefore its various parallel implementation strategies are discussed in next section. Let us algorithmically summarize the previous results.

ALGORITHMIC SCHEME

- Step 1.a: Set $\mathbf{G} := -\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{B}^\top$, $\mathbf{d} := \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}^\dagger \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{c}$, and $\mathbf{e} := -\mathbf{R}^\top \mathbf{f}$.
Step 1.b: Compute $\bar{\lambda}_{Im} := \mathbf{G}^\top (\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1} \mathbf{e}$.
Step 1.c: Set $\tilde{\mathbf{d}} := \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{F}\bar{\lambda}_{Im}$.
Step 1.d: Compute $\bar{\lambda}_{Ker}$ by solving $\mathbf{P}_G \mathbf{F} \lambda_{Ker} = \mathbf{P}_G \tilde{\mathbf{d}}$ on $Ker \mathbf{G}$.
Step 1.e: Set $\bar{\lambda} := \bar{\lambda}_{Im} + \bar{\lambda}_{Ker}$.
Step 2: Compute $\bar{\alpha} := (\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1} \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{F}\bar{\lambda})$.
Step 3: Compute $\bar{\mathbf{u}} := \mathbf{K}^\dagger(\mathbf{f} - \mathbf{B}^\top \bar{\lambda}) + \mathbf{R}\bar{\alpha}$.

Finally, we introduce the projected conjugate gradient method with preconditioning (PCGP) [3] that we use for computing λ_{Ker} in Step 1.d of Algorithmic scheme. Thus we want to compute λ_{Ker} by solving the system $\mathbf{P}_G \mathbf{F} \lambda_{Ker} = \mathbf{P}_G \tilde{\mathbf{d}}$ on $Ker \mathbf{G}$ with the cheap lumped preconditioner $\overline{\mathbf{F}^{-1}}$ [3] to \mathbf{F} . Let us note that for the orthonormal matrix \mathbf{B} (see Remark 2.1) we have

$$\overline{\mathbf{F}^{-1}} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{B}^\top. \quad (16)$$

ALGORITHM PCGP

1. Initialize

$$\mathbf{r}^0 = \tilde{\mathbf{d}}, \quad \lambda_{Ker}^0 = \mathbf{o}.$$

2. Iterate $k=1, 2, \dots$, until convergence

$$\text{Project } \mathbf{w}^{k-1} = \mathbf{P}_G \mathbf{r}^{k-1}.$$

$$\text{Precondition } \mathbf{z}^{k-1} = \overline{\mathbf{F}^{-1}} \mathbf{w}^{k-1}.$$

$$\text{Project } \mathbf{y}^{k-1} = \mathbf{P}_G \mathbf{z}^{k-1}.$$

$$\beta^k = (\mathbf{y}^{k-1})^\top \mathbf{w}^{k-1} / (\mathbf{y}^{k-2})^\top \mathbf{w}^{k-2}; \quad (\beta^1 = 0).$$

$$\mathbf{p}^k = \mathbf{y}^{k-1} + \beta^k \mathbf{p}^{k-1}; \quad (\mathbf{p}^1 = \mathbf{y}^0).$$

$$\alpha^k = (\mathbf{y}^{k-1})^\top \mathbf{w}^{k-1} / (\mathbf{p}^k)^\top \mathbf{F} \mathbf{p}^k.$$

$$\lambda_{Ker}^k = \lambda_{Ker}^{k-1} + \alpha^k \mathbf{p}^k.$$

$$\mathbf{r}^k = \mathbf{r}^{k-1} - \alpha^k \mathbf{F} \mathbf{p}^k.$$

3. $\bar{\lambda}_{Ker} = \lambda_{Ker}^k$.

Using TFETI in combination with PCGP algorithm we are able to find the solution of the original elastostatic problem in $O(1)$ matrix-vector multiplications independently of the problem size provided the ratio between the decomposition step H and the discretization step h is kept bounded. For more details about optimality see [3]. The generalization for non-symmetric systems may be found in [8].

4. Parallel implementation of TFETI

Parallelization of FETI/TFETI can be implemented mostly using SPMD technique – distributing matrix portions among processing units. This allows algorithms to be almost the same in sequential and parallel versions; only data structure implementation differs. Most of computations (subdomain problems) appearing are purely local and therefore parallelizable without any data transfers. However, if we want to accelerate also dual actions, some communication is needed due to primal-dual transition. Distribution of primal matrices is quite straightforward as every subblock reflects a subdomain. They can be implemented using general distributed column-block or row-block matrix type with nonzeros only in diagonal blocks. However, \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{R} possess nice block-diagonal layout and can be implemented more sophisticatedly using block-diagonal composite type where subblocks are ordinary sequential matrices and every core holds an array of them. This is nevertheless not directly implemented in the most of parallelization libraries.

Each of cores works with the local part associated with its subdomains. Natural effort using the massively parallel computers is to maximize the number of subdomains so that sizes of the subdomain stiffness matrices are reduced which accelerates their factorization and subsequent pseudoinverse application, which belong to the most time consuming actions. On the other hand, negative effect of that is an increase of null space dimension and number of Lagrange multipliers on subdomain interfaces, i.e. dual dimension, so that the bottleneck of the TFETI method is the application of the projector \mathbf{P}_G . The action time and the level of communication depend firstly on how \mathbf{G} is distributed and its action on a vector implemented (see Figure 2) and secondly how action of $(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^\top)^{-1}$ on a vector is implemented. Tested strategies were the following (see Figure 3):

1. Iterative: $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T$ is distributed across all processes, action of $(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T)^{-1}$ on a vector is solved by conjugate gradients with the Jacobi preconditioner, relative stopping tolerance is set to 1e-8, and max. number of iterations is limited to 500;
2. Direct: $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T$ is sequential, owned only by the master process, $(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T)^{-1}$ is implemented by PETSc built-in sequential direct LU solver;
3. Explicit: $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T$ is replicated to all processes, explicit inverse is obtained by PETSc built-in sequential direct LU solver applied on the local portion of the identity matrix so that $(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T)^{-1}$ is distributed across all processes.

We tested the above strategies only for distribution of \mathbf{G} into vertical blocks (variant B in Figure 2) because the opposite distribution (variant A) leads to relevant increase of communication cost. In numerical experiments, we show that the most promising one seems to be Strategy 3. Another possible strategy consists in parallel orthogonalization of \mathbf{G} leading unfortunately to its substantial fill in.

Fig. 2. \mathbf{G} matrix distributions and their actions on a vector.

Fig. 3. $(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{G}^T)^{-1}$ action strategies.

5. Numerical experiments

Let us start with comparing several strategies of the TFETI coarse problem solution on three different linear elasticity benchmarks:

1. two-dimensional elastostatic problem of the steel traverse of rectangular shape which is fixed on the left side and loaded by gravitational forces, the computational domain is divided into identical square subdomains and each subdomain is discretized by 64800 triangles;
2. three-dimensional elastostatic problem of the steel cube which is fixed on the left side and loaded on the top side, the computational domain is divided into identical cubic subdomains and each subdomain is discretized by 8000 bricks;
3. three-dimensional elastostatic real-world problem of the car engine block made of aluminium which is loaded inside the third cylinder (see Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Real world benchmark – the car engine block.

For benchmarking we used the HECToR Phase 3 (Cray XE6) machine at EPCC based on the latest AMD "Bulldozer" multicore processor architecture and the PETSc parallelization library with our optimized TFETI implementation.

In Table 1, we report the coarse problem preprocessing time, the solution time, all \mathbf{P}_G actions time, the number of PCGP iterations, and the total time without factorization of \mathbf{K} for all parallel strategies of the coarse problem solution described in the previous section. From the reported results we see immediately that the most promising strategy seems to be the Explicit one. Moreover, the coarse problem must be solved as accurately as possible, in opposite case PCGP can diverge.

Table 1. Performance of the coarse problem solution for all benchmarks.

CP strategy	Prepr. time (s)	Sol. time (s)	\mathbf{P}_G actions (s)	PCGP iter.	Tot. time (s)
Benchmark 1, 33mil. of unknowns, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{3072 \times 508032}$					
1. Iterative	0.0	13.1	10.1	86	13.1
2. Direct	0.8	3.7	0.6	86	4.4
3. Explicit	0.1	3.2	0.2	86	3.4
Benchmark 2, 14mil. of unknowns, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{3072 \times 1782816}$					
1. Iterative	1.0		DIVERGED		
2. Direct	5.9	10.0	1.7	29	15.9
3. Explicit	3.5	10.0	1.3	29	13.5
Benchmark 3, 3mil. of unknowns, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{6084 \times 472320}$					
1. Iterative	0.1		DIVERGED		
2. Direct	2.7	14.0	8.3	168	16.7
3. Explicit	3.2	11.8	5.5	170	15.0

The Total FETI scalability for Benchmark 1 is demonstrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Scalability behavior of PETSc FETI implementation tested on Benchmark 1.

Simultaneously we tested the scalability of the TFETI implementation in ELMER multiphysical simulation software on Benchmark 2. The scalability behaviour is shown in Figure 6, where the displayed weak-scaling computational times are achieved on the French Tier-0 system CURIE.

In both scalability tests, the solution time is expected to remain the same since the number of unknowns and cores (subdomains) increase by the same factor but for large decompositions the above-mentioned coarse problem solution starts to dominate. Therefore we plan to replace the standard TFETI method by its hybrid version which is expected to eliminate this drawback. The current tests with hybrid TFETI look very promising. None the less this standard FETI implementation in ELMER has demonstrated scalability for certain problems that were previously impossible to solve in parallel due to severe convergence problems.

The TFETI algorithm has been successfully applied also on nonlinear contact problems of engineering mechanics [10, 11, 12]. In Figure 8, the computed total displacement with 1.6 millions of unknowns of the yielding clamp connection of steel arched supports is depicted together with the used domain decomposition (see Figure 7). This type of construction is used to support the mining openings.

Fig. 6. Scalability behavior of ELMER FETI implementation tested on Benchmark 2.

Fig. 7. Yielding clamp connection - domain decomposition.

Fig. 8. Total displacement.

6. Summary

We described an efficient massively parallel implementation of our Total FETI method which was tested and optimized in PETSc and then implemented into Elmer. We highlighted all important implementation ingredients such as the effective regularization of singular subdomain stiffness matrices which improves conditioning and enables factorization using any standard Cholesky type decomposition method. This completely removes working with singular matrices. The scalability behavior has been shown up to thousands of cores on the HEC-ToR machine at EPCC and on the French Tier-0 system CURIE. Indeed for large decompositions the so-called coarse problem solution starts to dominate. This drawback can be eliminated by the so-called hybrid FETI method which we plan to implement into Elmer. The proposed algorithms were also successfully applied to the solution of large nonlinear contact problems discretized using TFETI.

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